

TECHNOLOGY OF FORMING FOREIGN LANGUAGE GRAMMAR SKILLS

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Abstract. *The ability to correctly combine words, change phrases depending on what you want to say at the moment is one of the most important conditions for using language as a means of communication. Mastering the grammar of the language being studied is important not only for the formation productive skills in oral and written speech, but also for understanding speech other people when listening and reading. Insufficient level of grammatical skills becomes an insurmountable barrier to formation of not only linguistic, but also speech and sociocultural competencies. With the help of a set of lexical units it is impossible to accurately convey an idea, since lexical units only name an object or phenomenon. The relationships between them are reflected in grammatical meanings. Grammar plays an organizing role. Expressed grammatically relationship between subject and predicate (subject and predicate), determined and defining action and object, temporary, spatial, causal connections of phenomena, the speaker's relationship to the expressed thought and the interlocutor.*

Keywords: *written speech, grammatical meanings, grammatical skills, means of communication.*

The importance of studying the grammar of a foreign language also lies in is that it helps to better understand the grammatical structure of the native language, develops logical thinking, observation, ability to analysis and generalization, i.e. in the process of studying it are realized developmental, educational and educational purposes of training. A system of stereotypes operates in the cerebral cortex, which dictates the rules for organizing words into a coherent whole. System of stereotypes determines the existence of an intuitive, unconscious grammar, which every person carries within himself in his native language. When studying foreign language, it is also necessary to launch the mechanism of stereotyping in based on the selected grammatical minimum, i.e. create an intuitive grammar that would contribute to the organization of speech in a foreign language. Mother tongue is the primary means of life communication, the assimilation of which is naturally motivated, since the native language is acquired in childhood in parallel with adaptation child to the environment. Foreign language is a secondary means communication, the use of which is not dictated by life necessity; mastering a foreign language begins in school age when the main means of communication - the native language - has already been formed, therefore, special efforts are required to induce learning motivation language. The native language is acquired in the natural language environment, from which the child without special efforts, i.e. involuntarily and in a short time, identifies patterns. Mastering a foreign language occurs in educational conditions in an environment alien to him. There is not enough base here for involuntary identification of patterns. Therefore, when mastering special attention to grammar in a school foreign language course should be given to theory and its optimal combination with speech practice, as well as the relationship between the voluntary form of attention and involuntary, i.e. consistent implementation of the principle consciousness. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the method is taken to be considered the way to achieve the goal, but it is used for designations of paths of different scales. The method is called fundamental direction in teaching foreign languages,

characterized by certain goals, content and principles teaching (grammar-translation method, direct method, etc.). The grammar-translation method was taught with the aim of developing logical thinking and the ability to read and translate texts.

According to this method, ownership language is mastery of grammar and vocabulary. Process improvement is understood as movement from one grammatical schemes to another. Thus, a teacher planning a course on this method, first thinks about what grammatical patterns he wants to illuminate. Then texts are selected for these topics, from which individual sentences are highlighted and the whole thing ends with a translation. First - from a foreign language to your native one, then - vice versa. Concerning text, usually this is the so-called artificial text, in which practically no importance is given to meaning: it is not so important that you say, it's how you say it that matters.

Modern lexico-grammatical methodology is aimed at teaching language as a system. First of all, the four main language skills - not only speaking and listening, but reading and letter. Therefore, students pay much attention to text analysis, writing expositions and essays. Moreover, everyone must understand structure and logic of a foreign language, be able to relate it to the native one, understand their similarities and differences. This is impossible without serious studying grammar and without practicing two-way translation. The history of methods of teaching foreign languages knows numerous and varied attempts to find the most rational method of teaching foreign languages. The oldest method was natural, which was no different from the method by which the child is taught their native language. The principle of consciousness underlies all methods used when mastering grammar; within each method, its own relationship between theory and practice. Application of “pure” theory without its confirmation by concrete facts of the functioning of grammatical phenomena, as well as “pure” practice without its comprehension, are not accepted in mastering grammar in a school foreign language course. Productive grammatical skill means the speaker’s ability to choose a model that is adequate to the speech task, and format it according to the norms of the given language. Speech task there is always a communicative intention to communicate something, about something convince, express an opinion. This or that serves to complete tasks. grammatical form. Therefore, emphasizes E.I. Passes, and should be associatively related to each other grammatical form and speech task.

If such a connection exists, then in the process of productive types of speech activity when a communicative task arises what emerges in consciousness is adequate and necessary at that moment grammatical form. Receptive grammatical skill should be understood as the ability of the reader (listener) to recognize grammatical forms the language being studied and correlate with their meaning. V.M. Filatov gives the following definition of the concepts “grammatical skill” and “grammatical ability”. Grammatical skill is the automated use of grammatical material in productive and receptive speech activity. Grammar skill is the flexible communication abilities of students to use mastered grammatical material when solving more complex communicative tasks in various types of speech activity.

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